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Typological analysis for knowledge and Conservation of Spread Built Heritage: A case study

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Abstract

Before carrying out any building refurbishment intervention, it is necessary to gather as much information as possible about the building itself and the built context surrounding it. This is a key factor in order to preserve the character of the built area in the design of the renovation intervention. For this reason, the first step to take is a field and archive survey to collect information and acquire knowledge about the existing shapes, materials, techniques and technologies. To do this, it may be helpful following a standardized procedure, consisting in simple steps, which allows identifying, at various scales (urban, building, technological, etc.) the invariant elements to be conserved, preserved and repeated in the project. This paper presents the application of a possible typical methodology to a real case belonging to the spread building heritage in Naples’ suburban area.

Keywords: Building typologies; Knowledge; Conservation; Spread built heritage

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